

SNo	Estimation of protein concentration		
	Cell free supernatant (CSF) collected at different growth Period of <i>Pediococcus acidilactici</i>	Total protein mg/mL	Purified Protein 3Kda mg/mL
1	24h - Prometabolite	48.32	5.3767
2	48h - Prometabolite	35.32	3.21

• $48.32\text{mg/mL} \times 1000\text{ mL} = 48.32\text{grams/ Liter} = \text{Total Protein}$
 • $5.37\text{mg/mL} \times 1000\text{ mL} = 5.370\text{ Gram/Liter} = \text{Target antimicrobial Peptide (Partially purified using size exclusion chromatography)}$

S4 b